

INTEGRATED EDUCATIONAL AND DIDACTICAL SYSTEMS AND TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10039887>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 20-October 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 23- October 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 25- October 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

integration, integrative approach, professional training of the future teacher-musician, multidisciplinary integration, integration of activism, integration of the educational and didactic system.

ABSTRACT

In the state, the integrative approach is presented as a basic organizational and constructive component of the professional training of the future teacher-musician, which is certainly relevant at the present stage of educational development. The professional training of future music teachers is considered as a sequence of actions in the unity of its components, such as theoretical, practical, methodological and cultural training. The author describes the implementation of the integrative approach in the following areas, such as interdisciplinary integration, integration of education and educational, professional, scientific, sociocultural education, integration of education and the didactic system. Interdisciplinary integration involves the establishment of interdisciplinary connections, which activates mental activity, increases the scientific level of education, develops cognitive interest, and ensures the perception of the whole picture. The integration of creativity and educational, professional, research, social and cultural creativity makes it possible to activate creative abilities and realize all the functions of education. The integration of the educational and didactic system allows for the professional training of future music teachers both as a pedagogical factor and as a social factor.

Introduction In modern conditions of the development of higher education and the implementation of federal state standards of the third generation (FGS 3++), it is necessary in the center to form the creative personality of a teacher-musician, the main goal of which is to organize effective work with students and satisfy the intellectual needs of society. This is possible when building the professional training of a future music teacher and the basis of an integrative approach.

The results of the implementation of the integrative approach are the systematization

of knowledge, the integrated application of knowledge, abilities and skills, strengthening the cognitive activity of students, achieving goals, and effectiveness. According to this study, the integrative approach as the main organizational and constructive component of the professional training of a future music teacher is relevant at the present stage of educational development.

Methodology. Integration and the possibilities of an integrative approach to increasing the effectiveness of professional training of specialists have recently increasingly attracted the attention of researchers. So, V.N. Maksimova believes that integration is a multi-level, complex study and a means of human development and individuality.

M. A. Nikolaeva, describing the integrative approach and the process of developing the professional competence of students - future advertising specialists, points out that integration is a means of acquiring new qualities through reflection and the versatility and multifunctionality of the future professional tasks [5]. The researcher points out that the use of an integrative approach increases the effectiveness of student learning through the integration of interdisciplinary, intradisciplinary, interpersonal and intrapersonal levels [5].

It is of interest to study the integration of the discipline of the humanitarian cycle as a way of developing general cultural competencies. In this case, we are talking about different methods of integration, such as establishing interdisciplinary connections in the course of studying one topic, creating interdisciplinary cases, etc. [6]. V.D. Purin makes a significant scientific contribution to the development of the problem of professional musical training and the substantiation of the application of the principle of integration in the pedagogical process of various areas of knowledge in the form of individual (point integration), several (block integration), many in total (integral integration) - associative, symbolic, categorical, etc. [7].

AVERAGE. Nasedkina and O.A. Kornilov believes that the future music teacher will have to play a big role in interdisciplinary integration and the development of professionalism. It is believed that in order to form an integral system of professional knowledge and skills of students, the actual integration of musical and theoretical knowledge, psychological and pedagogical knowledge and practical workshop skills is necessary [8].

Based on the work of the teachings that consider the use of integration and the integrative approach in the pedagogical system of vocational education, it can be noted that implementation in the integrative approach makes it possible to connect science and culture as a means of obtaining new knowledge. Birthdays personal and cultural meanings. At the same time, according to A.F. Malyshevsky, the educational process should be built on artistic models, where the image of a person is connected with culture, intuition with logic, knowledge with experience [9].

Let us turn to the next aspect of the problem under study and consider the main components of the professional training of future music teachers: theoretical, practical, methodological, cultural. According to researchers, the division of vocational education into various types is advisory in nature, since they are all interconnected. For example, it is too difficult to separate methodological and theoretical training, since the basis of theoretical training is methodological and one cannot exist without it. Practical training is impossible without methodological training, as it suggests the use of collaborative methods in school work conditions. The addition made by N.B. Krylova is very important in terms of the problem being analyzed. She believes that the professional training of future teachers will be carried

out through cultural studies, the purpose of which is to form values and different types of student experiences [10].

Theoretical training is the process of learning knowledge and expanding the range of interests of students. Theoretical training of future music teachers involves mastering such knowledge as knowledge of the essence of the processes of teaching and upbringing, its driving forces and patterns, principles, methods and forms of organization, etc. In practical training, all sets of knowledge are collected and the formation of skills and knowledge is carried out the fundamentals of professional activity in the process of real pedagogical activity of students in educational institutions. Methodological training is one of the most important tasks in the professional training of a future music teacher. It is enough for a modern music teacher to have practical experience and theoretical knowledge acquired during his student years; the teacher needs to turn to scientific theoretical knowledge and master the methods of scientific and pedagogical research.

Methodological knowledge, logical knowledge and methods of scientific and pedagogical research, basic research methods and skills are considered as the fundamental basis that helps the future specialist understand various innovations, concepts, new educational technologies, program development, teaching methods and much more. Number of proposals for implementation and professional details. Thus, the professional and pedagogical training of a future music teacher is an independent multi-component system, inclusive, one-sided, autonomous, and also interconnected forms of education. The autonomy of types of training determines the content component, commonality of purpose, principles, unity of internal organization, active interaction between themselves and the external environment give them integrative integrity.

Results. The purpose of this article is to identify the main ways to implement an integrative approach in the professional training of future music teachers, aimed at achieving a high level of training of future music teachers for professional activities. To achieve this goal, it is important to analyze the latest research on our chosen topic, identify the features of organizing the process of training future music teachers and determine the main ways to implement the integrative approach. We are considering the implementation of an integrative approach in such areas as interdisciplinary integration, integration of education and educational, professional, scientific, sociocultural education, integration of the educational and didactic system.

Interdisciplinary integration involves the establishment of interdisciplinary connections, which allows you to study disciplines in a coordinated manner and activates mental activity, increases the scientific level of education, develops cognitive connections, which allows you to study disciplines in a coordinated manner and activates mental activity, increases the scientific level of education, develops cognitive connections, and ensures acceptance solo katina. All this contributes to deepening the relationship between the discipline. The implementation of the integrative approach and pedagogical orientation of the subjects is based on special knowledge in the field of aesthetics, psychology, pedagogy, physiology, master's performing methods of teaching and learning. Sterzhnev's work as a teacher-musician is the implementation of musical and aesthetic education through the organization of the musical and pedagogical activities of the teacher himself and the educational and professional activities of schoolchildren.

Using knowledge of various subjects helps to integrate the educational process, improve the quality of professional training through the development of godly and scientific art of the modern world. This helps future music teachers use the acquired knowledge and adequately evaluate the phenomena being studied. For this reason, a music teacher must use innovative methods and techniques, as well as select thematic material that has educational value. Integration of creativity and educational, professional, research, social and cultural creativity as the second direction makes it possible to activate creative abilities and realize all the functions of educational and professional pedagogy; developmental – research; Educational is a sociocultural activity that is in constant interrelation.

Conclusion. The use of an integrative approach in the professional training of a future music teacher plays an important role in the modern competency-based education paradigm, since it allows us to combine all components of professional training into a single whole, which complements and expands the capabilities of each component of the overall system. This allows you to use all the possibilities of professional training, implement special courses and training on the principles of integration into university education programs, include future music teachers in pedagogical and cultural-creative activities, which allows you to gain practical experience in all aspects of your future work and the use of all components by future teachers -musicians in an integrative approach and professional training.

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